

AN EDUCATOR'S TOOLKIT:
USING ETHNIC STUDIES TO ENRICH CLASSROOMS

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Abstract

Education is meant to teach young learners more about the world around them. However, learning about the world from a very fortunate person's lens does not always help students who are part of more marginalized communities. Taking current literature into consideration, the teaching practice of implementing ethnic studies into all fields of study for education ranging from kindergarten to the sixth grade can greatly benefit students. Findings from this literature review indicate that ethnic studies can be implemented into lessons for any subject and have a tremendously positive impact on students. At the end of the literature review, sample lesson plans from various grade levels and subject matters are included as an example of just how many ways ethnic studies can be implemented into a standard curriculum.

Key Words: education, ethnic studies, diversity, curriculum, elementary

Introduction

Elementary-aged children are learning many concepts for the first time. Some of these concepts are fundamental, such as learning to share, while others are strictly educational, like learning a scientific theory. However, elementary-age children should be taught and continue to learn different features of cultures other than their own. Teaching a class with only one cultural background, race, or ethnicity in mind means that students who do not fall into that category may become less engaged, and grades may begin to fall. Encouraging educators to implement ethnic studies into K-6 classrooms can benefit students academically and socially through higher grades and less behavior issues (Tintiango-Cubales et al. 2015).

What is Ethnic Studies? (And Other Definitions)

Education has many terms that the general public may not be aware of. The term pedagogy can be described as how teachers provide information to students as well as what ways in which the students present this knowledge. Furthermore, the decolonization of education in America was, and still is, a huge motivator for ethnic studies movements (Tintiango-Cubales, et al., 2014). Decolonization is described as undoing the ways education of the past had expanded upon colonial ideas. Challenging those practices within an educational context can assist in creating a new standard for education today (CYS UVic 2016). Referring to ethnic studies means educating people on the history, culture, and traditions of people of color in America, as well as the role these individuals held in building the United States from the ground up (Nguyen 2021; Gonzalez 2021).

However, ethnic studies is not just a curriculum, it is an entire movement. Ethnic studies began as people of color within academic settings pushing for better representation within curriculum and course materials. These individuals wanted the educational focus to shift from

the Western European viewpoints to a perspective that looked critically at race, power, and accessibility. More specifically, students within the Black Student Union at San Francisco State University pushed for the validity of ethnic studies in higher educational settings. Also at San Francisco State University, the Third World Liberation Front was created as students from Asian, Latin, and African backgrounds began to address the tension between minority identities and the university. These groups, through lots of struggle and striking, were able to create a deal with San Francisco State University in 1969 where the university would create an ethnic studies department, which was the first of its kind at the time. This leads to decades of progress being made, most notably in 2020 where it became a requirement of all students within the California State University system to take an ethnic studies course (Ehsanipour 2020). Even more recently, it has now become a requirement for California high schoolers to enroll in an ethnic studies course in order to graduate.

The Lack of Ethnic Studies

Many grow up with the privilege of a good education in a great school district, but even then, something can be missing. The missing piece to many educational careers is the perspectives of non-White people. Many teachers within certain school districts also may not advocate for their students of color, so the student body may not have exposure to advocacy within an educational environment. Students should be encouraged to be exposed to more diverse literature, see historical events from different perspectives, and learn to be advocates for themselves and others. The goal within researching the implementation of ethnic studies is to bring new material, perspectives, and ways of thinking into classrooms with students from any background.

Including ethnic studies in the curriculum presented in classrooms is not only enriching for students but also thought-provoking for the educator as they begin to include different lessons that pertain to the cultural backgrounds of their students. Wiggan and Watson (2016), for example, point out that the typical public education found in the United States is a story of the predominant culture modified by each state's standards. With the strong influence of White, European culture within the public school system, students rarely get the opportunity to explore historically significant topics from other cultures. This is especially prevalent in literature, history, and the arts. Systemic issues within public education are also a huge reason why students in underserved communities exhibit lower understandings of topics through measurable factors such as test scores. A specific example of this would be the myth of Black students being inferior to their White counterparts, which really started during the colonization of what is now the United States of America (Charles, 2019). The goal in doing this in the colonies was to purposely create a dominant culture and societal standard for what can be deemed normal.

Marie Charles (2019) explains that this idea of what is normal carries through to modern times where many educators still treat their Black students poorly when exhibiting behavior that non-Black students are at times rewarded for. Furthermore, Charles also points out that within educational and non-educational environments alike, Black history cannot be condensed into one month of history, but should be taught throughout the lessons in order to create a more holistic view and help students understand that all history is connected. Both of these articles have the strength of pointing out the shortcomings of the educational system that is most prevalent in the United States, but also including ways in which educators can improve the lesson quality through methods such as supporting students in learning about topics they are interested in as well as being culturally responsive in order to increase student engagement and achievement.

Many educators may argue that implementing ethnic studies is unnecessary in classes that do not talk about culture, such as math or science. However, it is equally important in these courses as it would be in an English or history class because the baseline is ensuring student representation in all aspects of education. If children do not see themselves represented in areas of math and science, there is a chance they are less likely to feel motivated to explore future career options in STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics). This can lead to an even smaller number of under-represented minority groups, or URMs, entering the STEM field in the future (Barakat 2022).

There is quite a bit of pushback coming from many individuals across the country when it comes to the concept of implementing ethnic studies into their childrens' education. Looking at Orange County, California specifically, an ethnic studies curriculum has been unanimously approved in Los Alamitos Unified School District, but not without the flood of community naysayers. Community members described ethnic studies as being filled with hate for the United States and believe that the goal of ethnic studies is to teach children that all white people are racist (Smith 2021). Due to the lack of ethnic studies across educational levels in years past, parents and other older members of communities spread across America see ethnic studies as an enemy, as something that will brainwash the youth and create monsters out of white people. Ethnic studies, by definition, is no such enemy, which highlights the importance of community education and advocacy when talking about ethnic studies. In the Placentia-Yorba Linda Unified School District, school board president Leandra Blades, who was present for the riots at the Capitol on January 6th, 2021, denounced the educational goals of California as a whole, calling it nothing more than left-wing ideologies. Once again, a case of miseducation, or no education whatsoever, of ethnic studies. The implementation of ethnic studies would begin a new cycle of

education for a generation to use and improve the world around them.

Talking About Cultural Diversity in the Classroom

Throughout a students' academic career from kindergarten to their senior year of high school, one might wonder how many cultures they were introduced to in a productive way. Many people hear about cultures in passing, but how many educators dedicate lessons to influential individuals from cultures that differ from those of their students? Each student in a classroom, no matter the grade level, can greatly benefit from learning about other cultures. Karen Howard (2018) explains that students become much more eager to learn as they are exposed to different cultures. It is also beneficial for students as they expand on their general social understanding.

Students can also benefit from having educators who work towards being antiracists and speaking out in order to ensure quality educational experiences for all students and fellow staff.

Educators who integrate ethnic studies into their lessons can include more of their students in conversations as well as ensure that each student can get a chance to talk to the class about their cultural background for educational purposes. On top of implementing ethnic studies into everyday activities, teaching for social justice through antiracist rhetoric can also teach children more about advocacy for themselves or their classmates. School districts have the power to create curriculum plans within elementary schools that are from diverse perspectives, antiracist, and work to decolonize the classroom.

Being antiracist within an educational environment is step one in teaching for social justice, and can also be another way to promote ethnic studies while teaching. Teaching is a form of advocacy, and it is a teacher's job to ensure that students know that they are welcomed, supported, and that their struggles are validated. Some definitions are necessary for reaching a full understanding of the magnitude of this movement. Ibram X. Kendi (2019) devotes the first full chapter of his book *How to Be an Antiracist* to certain definitions regarding racism and becoming an antiracist individual. He first describes racism as “a marriage of racist policies and racist ideas that produces and normalizes racial inequities” (pp. 17-8). A racist policy is described as any sort of policy, rule, or measure that continues the cycle of inequality between different races. Inherently racist policies in schools could manifest themselves in the form of not admitting students of color into gifted programs, not hiring educators of color even if they are qualified, and punishing students of color for behaviors that their White peers exhibit but are not punished for. Kendi (2019) also goes forward to explain what an antiracist policy is, stating that it is a policy, rule, law, or measure that promotes equity between different races.

It appears to be a universal experience for many educators who wish to implement an ethnic studies-focused pedagogy into their classrooms. Many educators are dependent on the school district to supply teaching materials such as the curriculum, but there may not always be flexibility within the material provided to cater to students' individual needs. A student's home life can be far different than the material taught in schools, so trying to bridge the gap between the two lives can improve student engagement in the classroom since they will be able to relate to the content more (Wiggans & Watson, 2016). Also, it is up to educators to release any racial biases they may have. An example is how some educators still hold onto the notion that Black students are less capable of learning than White students due to stereotypes created during the colonial era of the United States (Charles, 2019). Furthermore, within underserved communities, a lack of antiracist educators can result in less advocacy for students and their families. Being an antiracist individual is more than just identifying right versus wrong, but it goes forward into teaching others how to advocate for themselves and identifying resources that can be of assistance to a community.

Bringing Ethnic Studies into Our Classrooms

Education is multifaceted and requires constant reexamination considering the diverse population of students across America. Ethnic studies is an especially effective way to not only include students' backgrounds in lessons but also to validate their lived experiences and help to further engage them inside the classroom. Between teaching educators new ways to be proactive in the classroom and learning to acknowledge the White Euro-centric views that American public schooling has, the future of education is looking bright. Teaching for social justice, especially, can bring a new perspective to teachers and students alike as they begin to apply what they learn in class to the communities around them. In conclusion, creating a safe classroom

environment for all students means that educators and administrative employees must identify the shortcomings in typical education when it comes to race and culture, work to fix internal biases, encourage students to question Western ideals and why non-Western countries are often not included in the conversation, and inviting others to look into the historical significance of pieces of culture that have the greatest impacts.

Lesson Plans that Implement Ethnic Studies

The following pages are going to consist of sample lesson plans that implement ethnic studies. The first one is a lesson plan for a thirty minute lesson in a kindergarten class learning about Indigenous People's Day and the history behind it changing from being called Columbus Day. The second lesson plan is a forty five minute lesson for third graders learning about natural hazards and how lower income communities suffer as a consequence. These lesson plans are hypothetical in nature, but the sentiment is strong that ethnic studies can be implemented into any subject and any class while still following the standards set by the state or school district.

Lesson Plan 1: Kindergarten Social Studies

Overview:

This lesson is meant to introduce the kindergarten class to the Indigenous tribes that inhabited the land we currently live on. As Indigenous People's Day is fast approaching, it is important that we know more about the individuals who helped to shape America beyond just Christopher Columbus. As we have already learned about Columbus, it is time to learn more about the people whose lives were strongly impacted by his arrival.

Time Allotted:

30 minutes

CA Content Standards Covered:

- K.6.1. Identify the purposes of, and the people and events honored in, commemorative holidays, including the human struggles that were the basis for the events (e.g., Thanksgiving, Independence Day, Washington's and Lincoln's Birthdays, Martin Luther King Jr. Day, Memorial Day, Labor Day, Columbus Day, Veterans Day).
- K.6.3. Understand how people lived in earlier times and how their lives would be different today (e.g., getting water from a well, growing food, making clothing, having fun, forming organizations, living by rules and laws).

Materials and Media:

- Land acknowledgement worksheet
- Prepare information about local tribes prior to lesson - focus on those which resided on the land that the school is on
- Have map of tribe locations up on separate tab
- Also have GoNoodle ready to go for brain breaks as needed

Warm Up and Introduction (10 minutes):

- Once students have finished transition from previous subject matter or a break, bring them back with an attention grabber
 - “Class class” “yes yes,” “1, 2, 3, eyes on me” “1, 2, eyes on you,” etc...
- Ask students if anyone remembers who Christopher Columbus was from previous lesson
 - Who was he? What boats did he bring over to the Americas? What continent did he think he had landed on?
 - Most importantly, who did he encounter upon landing here?
- Do we know any names of Indigenous tribes that have resided on the land that is now the United States?
- Land Acknowledgement:
 - Pass out land acknowledgement worksheet (included at end)
 - First blank is for student name, second is for tribe name
 - As a class, look at a map of where different tribes have lived
 - Point out our school's location on the map – whose land are we on?
 - Also can use <https://native-land.ca/> for extra specifics
 - Have students fill out the blanks on the worksheet for their name and tribe names

****Brain break! Use <https://www.gonoodle.com/> to give students a chance to get up and move****

Lesson Focus (15 minutes):

- Have information about tribes of the area ready to be presented (locations will vary)
- Include key information about houses that were built, foods they ate, and native plants they relied on.
- Have students fill out worksheet with that information

- Explain that while these groups may have built certain types of homes and eaten certain foods a long time ago, Indigenous individuals are still living in the United States today.
 - Some live on reservations, others may live right next door in the modern houses we know today. They wear clothing, drive cars, and eat foods that we are familiar with.
 - ****Important to inform students of the modern existence of Indigenous peoples so they do not grow up thinking that these groups of people are obsolete.**

****Brain break! Use Go Noodle to give students a chance to get up and move****

Closure/Debrief (5 minutes):

- Ask class questions relating to lesson focus
 - What tribes lived on the land we currently live on?
 - What types of houses did these tribes build?
 - What plants did these tribes rely on for food? What about plants for non-food uses?
- Any additional questions relating to lesson?
- Do one final brain break before transitioning to next subject or break

I, _____,
acknowledge that we live and attend
school on land that belonged to the
_____ tribe.

What types of houses did people in this tribe live in?

What types of foods did these people eat?

What types of plants did this tribe rely on for
everyday living?

Lesson Plan 2: Third Grade Science

Overview:

Previous lessons have covered what environmental factors can lead to natural disasters such as floods or earthquakes, but how do these events affect the communities involved? This lesson breaks out into a more human geography-focused discussion as we expand on our knowledge of natural hazards and the unfortunate affects that they have on lower income communities, as well as ways to advocate for these communities on a local and national level.

Time Allotted:

35 minutes

CA Content Standards Covered:

- 3-ESS3-1. Make a claim about the merit of a design solution that reduces the impacts of a weather-related hazard.* [Clarification Statement: Examples of design solutions to weather-related hazards could include barriers to prevent flooding, wind resistant roofs, and lightning rods.]
- ESS3.B: Natural Hazards; A variety of natural hazards result from natural processes. Humans cannot eliminate natural hazards but can take steps to reduce their impacts. (3-ESS3-1) (Note: This Disciplinary Core Idea is also addressed by 4-ESS3-2.)

Materials and Media:

- Crash Course: Geography #27 (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-FBq51E1Kz0>)
 - Have ready to play in separate tab, to be paused at 5:41
- Crash course follow-along worksheet (see attached at end)
- Potentially have a typed out transcript for extra accessibility to video content

- Send video link to classroom community on services such as ClassDojo or similar - can be used as review tool along with other class materials required

Warm Up and Introduction (5 minutes):

- Once students have finished transition from previous subject matter or a break, bring them back with an attention grabber
 - “Class class” “yes yes,” “1, 2, 3, eyes on me” “1, 2, eyes on you,” etc...
- On whiteboard, smartboard, or easel-sized paper pad, draw a large circle in the middle to begin a mind map
 - In that circle, write “natural hazards”
 - Ask class for examples of natural hazards/disasters
 - Examples include earthquakes, avalanches, drought, floods, etc...

****Brain break! Use Go Noodle to give students a chance to get up and move****

Lesson Focus (25 minutes):

- Watch CrashCourse's *Natural Hazards: Crash Course Geography #27* from beginning-5:41
- Have worksheets ready to be handed out before video. Make sure video is up and ready to go, and be ready to stop video at listed time.
- After video, class discussion:
 - Why do lower income communities struggle more after a natural hazard hits the community?
 - Lower income → less resources
 - Political climate can contribute to lack of resources

- Race/racism can also contribute to the creation of these low income communities
- See <https://www.usnews.com/news/health-news/articles/2022-06-22/disaster-disparities-natural-hazards-climate-change-threaten-underserved-communities>
- What impact did the New Orleans' "White Flight" of the 50s-70s have on the communities that were built in the following years?
 - White people took their money and resources out of these areas - leaving people of color/other marginalized groups to use what they did have to build the communities. Lack of money resulted in lack of resources
- What can the government (local and national) do to assist these communities following a natural hazard?
 - See <https://www.justice.gov/file/1376311/download>, potentially simplify info down or just use as talking points for discussion

****Brain break! Use Go Noodle to give students a chance to get up and move****

Closure/Debrief (5 minutes):

- Ask class questions relating to lesson focus
 - What are some examples of natural hazards?
 - Can natural hazards be created by humans? Why not?
 - What types of communities suffer the greatest losses due to natural hazards?
 - What is one way the government offers assistance to these communities?
 - What more can be done to help these communities for the years following the natural hazard event happening?

- Any additional questions relating to the lesson?
- Do one final brain break before transitioning to next subject or break

Name: _____

Crash Course: Natural Hazards "Follow-Along"

1. The world works as a combination of _____, _____, and _____ systems.
2. The 2 main components of natural hazards are the actual physical event AND the _____ on humans.
3. What are 3 examples of physical events mentioned in the video?
 - a. _____
 - b. _____
 - c. _____
4. Is a physical event, such as a flood, a bigger danger in an unpopulated or populated area? _____
5. True or False: Natural hazards can also be caused by humans (circle one)
 - a. True
 - b. False
6. To evaluate a natural hazard, we need to evaluate (bold headings):
 - a. _____
 - b. _____
 - c. _____

7. In New Orleans, what communities are at a higher risk of danger when natural disasters hit? _____
8. Are disaster preparation/response programs readily available to individuals in lower income communities? (Yes/No) _____
9. _____ is the phenomenon that happened between the 1950s-70s in New Orleans that left parts of the city with very little money and resources.
10. Natural hazards are also being described as “a complex web of interactions among _____, _____, and _____, characterized by multiple causes and consequences.”

Name: KEY

Crash Course: Natural Hazards "Follow-Along"

1. The world works as a combination of physical,
biological, and social systems.
2. The 2 main components of natural hazards are the actual
physical event AND the potential impact on humans.
3. What are 3 examples of physical events mentioned in the
video?
 - a. **
 - b. **
 - c. **

**Can be any three of the following: heat waves, cyclones,
earthquakes, volcanic eruptions, floods, droughts, or mudslides.

4. Is a physical event, such as a flood, a bigger danger in an
unpopulated or populated area? populated
5. True or False: Natural hazards can also be caused by humans
(circle one)
 - a. True
 - b. **False**
6. To evaluate a natural hazard, we need to evaluate (bold
headings):
 - a. magnitude

b. time

c. space

7. In New Orleans, what communities are at a higher risk of danger when natural disasters hit? poorer/low income/low SES
8. Are disaster preparation/response programs readily available to individuals in lower income communities? (Yes/No) NO
9. White Flight is the phenomenon that happened between the 1950s-70s in New Orleans that left parts of the city with very little money and resources.
10. Natural hazards are also being described as "a complex web of interactions among peoples, environemnts, and technologies, characterized by multiple causes and consequences."

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